

1 Kdm6b functions in lineage specification of the TE in hES cells.
2

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 Kdm6b as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Mallaney, C., Ostrander, E.L., Celik, H., Kramer, A.C., Martens, A., Kothari, A., Koh, W.K.,
12 Haussler, E., Iwamori, N., Gontarz, P. and Zhang, B., 2019. Kdm6b regulates context-dependent
13 hematopoietic stem cell self-renewal and leukemogenesis. *Leukemia*, 33(10), pp.2506-2521.
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28